

EVALUATION OF THE ONE SAFE FUTURE (1SF) PROGRAM OR OPLAN LIKAS IN CAMARIN RESIDENCES 1, CALOOCAN CITY: A BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN ACTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated if the government's One Safe Future Program achieved its objective – providing safe, secure, affordable, and decent resettlement housing with basic services, facilities, and infrastructures to Informal Settler Families (ISFs) in Camarin Residences1, Caloocan City. It determined the extent of ISF's participation in the program's pre-, actual, and post-relocation phases and the relocatees' satisfaction levels in socioeconomic, environmental, institutional, and infrastructure aspects. The study gathered the issues encountered by the respondents and recommendations to improve their situation. The theoretical underpinning is "A Ladder of Citizen Participation" by Sherry R. Arnstein (1969), and New Public Management Theory by Osborne and Gaebler (1992). The concurrent triangulation design mixed methodology was employed. The instruments used were a researcher-made survey questionnaire and a focus group discussion with the implementers and beneficiaries. The results revealed that the extent of participation using the lens of Arnstein (1969) is in the 4th level or Consultation. Per Arnstein (1969), Consultation if not combined with other modes of participation, offers no assurance that citizen concerns and ideas will be considered. Since the relocation in 2015, there were still several lacking services and facilities on the site and the relocatees still face several problems. The action plan developed based on the results could be considered as a refinement to the set of strategies, policies, and programs of the government that would directly address the needs of the people and the problem of urban housing in Metro Manila to achieve inclusive growth, improved human development, and total community improvement.

Keywords: Informal Settler, Citizen participation, Relocation, Resettlement Site, Urban Housing

INTRODUCTION

Interrelated factors, including rapid population growth, rural-to-urban migration, inadequate affordable housing for the urban poor, weak governance, economic vulnerability, discrimination, marginalization, and displacement resulting from conflict, natural disasters, and climate change, present significant challenges to urban development and human settlements. These issues contribute to the proliferation of informal settlements (UN-Habitat, 2009, 2011, 2013). According to Williams, Costa, Sutherland, Celliers, and Scheffran (2019), uncontrolled urbanization is a key driver of these informal settlements. This phenomenon exacerbates the vulnerability of the urban poor, who are often situated in high-risk areas with substandard infrastructure and poor housing quality, making them particularly susceptible to the impacts of natural disasters (John R., 2020).

Informal settlers are individuals who lack security of tenure and face significant challenges in accessing basic services such as electricity, potable water, communication, transportation, and income-generating opportunities (Simiyu, Cairncross, & Swilling, 2019; Mensah, 2022). Additionally, they often have limited access to healthcare services (Palacios et al., 2022) and experience poor conditions in schools and health centers (Zulch, Musefuwa, & Yacim, 2019). Their housing is typically of low quality (Somvanshi, 2015) and is frequently located in geographically and environmentally hazardous areas (UN-Habitat, 2015), such as reclaimed landfills with polluted water (Somvanshi, 2015; Palacios et al., 2022) or near high-voltage towers. These conditions exacerbate the vulnerability of the urban poor, who are often situated in high-risk areas with substandard infrastructure and poor housing quality, making them particularly susceptible to the impacts of natural disasters (John R., 2020).

As the primary duty bearer and central actor in human development, the government is responsible for addressing the housing and shelter needs of its citizens, who are the rights holders. This entails ensuring that adequate, affordable, and secure housing is available, aligning with the fundamental rights and needs of the population.

In 2010, after the onslaught of Tropical Storm Ondoy in 2009, then-President Benigno S. Aquino III directed the creation of the Informal Settler Families-National Technical Working Group (ISF-NTWG) led by the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) to ensure safe and flood-resilient permanent housing solutions for ISFs living in danger areas in the National Capital Region (NCR).

In 2011, the One Safe Future (1SF) Program also known as the Oplan LIKAS (Lumikas para Iwas Kalamidad at Sakit) was launched to relocate ISFs living in high-risk areas and along major waterways in Metro Manila. This initiative was implemented for five (5) years from 2011 to 2016 with a fifty billion (PhP 50B) fund to address the

requirements of ISFs living in danger areas to safe settlements. The 1SF Program included the provision of housing units, community facilities, and socio-economic, community support programs encompassing on-site, in-city, near-city, and off-city resettlement projects.

The study assessed the extent of participation of the affected ISFs and stakeholders throughout various phases of the Oplan LIKAS Program. This included the pre-relocation phase (initiation and planning), the actual relocation phase (implementation and monitoring), and the post-relocation phase (evaluation). These phases represent the core components of the project development cycle.

The study also evaluated the level of satisfaction among affected families regarding the implementation of the Oplan LIKAS Program, focusing on socioeconomic, environmental, institutional, and infrastructure aspects. To measure satisfaction, a researcher-developed survey questionnaire was administered, and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted with key implementers and beneficiaries. These methods were employed to assess respondents' satisfaction with the program, identify areas of concern encountered by relocatees at resettlement sites, and gather suggestions and recommendations for improving their conditions.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of participation of the affected ISFs in the pre-, actual, and post-relocation phases of the 1SF Program?
2. What is the level of satisfaction of the ISFs with the program's implementation in terms of the following variables:
 - 2.1 Socioeconomic Aspect;
 - 2.2 Environmental Aspect;
 - 2.3 Institutional Aspect; and
 - 2.4 Infrastructure Aspect?
3. What are the areas of concern that the respondents encountered at the resettlement site in terms of the following variables:
 - 3.1 Socioeconomic Aspect;
 - 3.2 Environmental Aspect;
 - 3.3 Institutional Aspect; and
 - 3.4 Infrastructure Aspect?
4. What are the recommendations of the respondents to address the issues and concerns they encountered at the resettlement site?
5. Based on the study's findings, what are the programs of action for the Enhanced Program on Relocation?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a mixed-methods approach, which integrates both quantitative and qualitative methodologies within a single research framework. This approach involves the collection and analysis of numerical data (quantitative) and narrative data (qualitative)

to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. By combining these methods, the study aims to capture the context and subjective experiences of participants while also allowing for broader generalization of the findings to a larger population (researchmethod.net).

In the study, data were analyzed using a concurrent triangulation design. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously and then compared to identify areas of agreement and discrepancy. This integration of findings aimed to provide a more holistic understanding of the research problem.

Quantitative data were collected using a researcher-designed survey questionnaire, while qualitative data were gathered through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with the program's key implementers and beneficiaries. To ensure the accuracy of the findings, the results were presented to the respondents for validation. Additionally, a document review was conducted to supplement the data collection process.

In the study, the researcher transcribed the FGDs with the key implementers and beneficiaries and applied a narrative analysis technique to distill interviews into a set of core narratives. In the first step, the narrative blocks of the transcribed data were inductively coded. The second step involved grouping the narratives with the same codes and noting their similarities and differences. The third step involved creating and nesting the codes according to the story structure framework. The fourth step involved delving into the story structures and collating them with each life event code. The similarities and differences were coded to further enrich the analysis. In the fifth step, the narrative blocks were broken into story structures, switched and read between the narrative blocks as a whole without losing sight of the overarching narrative, and dove into each story structure code and paid attention to how these relate across a life event. In the last step, the life-event structures were analyzed to come up with the core narratives.

The quantitative data were organized and categorized according to the phases of the relocation process, facilitating a more detailed analysis and presentation. The data were then presented in relation to the study's key variables: socioeconomic, environmental, infrastructure, and institutional aspects.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The study's total population comprised 883 families resettled in Camarin Residences 1 (CamRes 1), Barangay 175, Caloocan City. These families had previously lived along the Tullahan River, Estero de Maypajo, and other waterway tributaries, including the Caloocan-Navotas River, Casili, and Maligaya Creek. Using Slovin's Formula, 276 families from the CamRes1 resettlement site were selected as respondents.

Description of the Respondents

The respondents for this study included household heads, who are either male or female and typically serve as the primary income earners for their families. These

individuals are beneficiaries or awardees of the housing units provided through the resettlement program.

For the FGD, the participants included key members of the Caloocan City Inter-Agency Committee composed of the District Manager of the National Housing Authority (NHA), Bagong Silang, officials from Barangay 175, the Officer-in-Charge of the Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)-formerly known as the Urban Poor and Affairs Office (UPAO), the Officer-in-Charge of the City Planning and Development Department (CPDD), the Action Officer of the City Social Welfare and Development Department (CSWDD), and representatives from the offices of the City Administrator and City Engineering.

Additionally, FGDs with beneficiaries included the Homeowners' Association (HOA) President from Buildings A to J of CamRes 1.

Instrumentation

The researcher utilized the following instruments in data collection: (1) a researcher-made survey questionnaire; (2) FGD with the program implementers; and (3) FGD with the beneficiaries.

With the assistance of the Homeowners' Association (HOA) officers, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaires to respondents from each building.

The survey questionnaire comprised four sections: (1) The first section examined the extent of affected families' participation in the pre-, actual, and post-relocation phases of the 1SF Program; (2) The second section assessed the level of satisfaction of the affected families with the program focusing on socioeconomic, environmental, institutional, and infrastructure aspects. It evaluated their level of satisfaction with the community facilities, social infrastructure, and basic services at the resettlement site; (3) The third section identified the challenges faced by relocatees at the resettlement site, specifically regarding socioeconomic, environmental, institutional, and infrastructure aspects. Respondents selected the most relevant answers from the provided options; and (4) the final part gathered the respondents' suggestions and recommendations for improving the program and addressing their concerns, directed at the government and other stakeholders involved in the 1SF Program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The extent of Participation of the Affected ISFs in the Pre-relocation, Actual relocation, and Post-relocation Phases of the 1SF Program

The survey results indicated that informal settler families (ISFs) and affected families attended the general assemblies organized by the Local Inter-Agency Committee (LIAC). All implementers confirmed that the ISFs actively participated in meetings where the

program and relocation processes were discussed. Additionally, it was reported that the National Housing Authority (NHA) facilitated field trips to various resettlement sites, including those in Cavite, Trece Martires, Pandi, and Norzagaray. Ultimately, the ISFs had the opportunity to select their preferred resettlement site.

Sherry R. Arnstein's (1969) Ladder of Citizen Participation categorizes activities such as consultation dialogues, meetings, and information dissemination using various platforms as forms of non-participation or Level 1 Manipulation, a course some use to substitute genuine participation. At this level, the government collects information and builds public relations, and rapport with the people to establish their participation in the program. Respondents recommended that the government should engage affected families in all stages of the program, with particular emphasis on their involvement during the planning process.

In accordance with Part I.1 of the ISF-NTWG Joint Memorandum Circular No. 01 Series of 2013, the relocation of informal settler families (ISFs) is to be carried out on-site, near-city, or in-city, in line with the People's Plan and ensuring adequate and genuine consultation with the families. In 2015, the LIAC conducted a three-day Relocation and Resettlement Action Plan (RRAP) formulation for ISFs living in structures within the three-meter easement and other legally defined danger areas of the city. During the RRAP formulation, the Civil Society Organizations (CSO) representatives presented their People's Plans for consideration and potential mainstreaming in the city's RRAP, provided they complied with city ordinances and policies.

According to Arnstein (1969), meetings or workshops often involve a select group of individuals who are deemed suitable to provide input on the plans. While these sessions allow some level of contribution from less privileged participants, the ultimate authority to evaluate and make final decisions remains with the powerholders. Arnstein (2019) further argues that consultation alone, without integrating other forms of participation, cannot ensure that citizen concerns and ideas are genuinely considered. When powerholders restrict input solely to this level, participation becomes a mere formality rather than a substantive process.

Cooperative Arrangement and Collaborative Undertaking. In the implementation of the 1SF, or Oplan LIKAS Program, the LIAC, composed of the officials of the City of Caloocan, the officials of the barangay, and other functionaries, NGAs, and CSOs, collaborated and coordinated in pursuit of a successful implementation of the program.

Engagements in Various Undertakings. The NHA facilitated house-tripping to several resettlement sites including Trece Martirez, Norzagaray, Pandi Bulacan, and CamRes1 allowing the people the opportunity to select their preferred location. Key implementers stated that they organized *Kumustahan* dialogue and general assemblies with the relocated families to assess their conditions at the resettlement site. These assemblies were conducted regularly and continue to be held to ensure ongoing support and address any emerging issues.

2. Level of Satisfaction with the Implementation of the 1SF Program in terms of Socioeconomic, Environmental, Institutional, and Infrastructure Aspects

The socioeconomic assessment of the relocatees in CamRes 1 yielded a weighted mean score of 2.71, reflecting a Satisfactory rating. This assessment revealed that 12 out of 18 essential services and facilities were available and accessible at the site. This included electricity, an elementary school, a high school, a police station, a barangay hall, a university, a hospital, a church, a health center, and a fire station. Additionally, the presence of roving police officers and barangay enforcers contributed to the overall assessment.

The environmental assessment of the relocatees in CamRes 1 resulted in a total weighted mean score of 2.47, which is categorized as Unsatisfactory. The data revealed that the respondents were unsatisfied with the Sewerage Treatment Plant (STP) in CamRes 1. Respondents shared that the STP's treatment of wastewater and sewage emitted a foul odor in the vicinity. Respondents reported that the STP's wastewater and sewage treatment processes emitted a persistent foul odor, which was perceived as a potential health hazard due to continuous exposure. Additionally, issues with garbage collection were noted: while each building is equipped with a garbage bin, its limited capacity leads to frequent overflow. The lack of waste segregation exacerbates the problem, causing further complaints from residents about unpleasant smells.

In terms of the Institutional aspect, the respondents stated that although they were organized and officially recognized within their building, the HOA lacked autonomy in decision-making. All decisions concerning the site shall be coursed through and coordinated with the LGU and/or the NHA. One of the principles of New Public Management (NPM) according to Osborne and Gaebler (1992) is decentralization, which localizes government power and grants more freedom to organizations or sectors. The aforementioned scenario maintains a hierarchical structure, commonly referred to as a bureaucratic version of conventional administration. This is in contrast to the concept of NPM, which focuses on the decentralization of power from rigid, hierarchical bureaucratic systems to flexible and dynamic managerial support systems. According to Gaebler and Osborne (1992), the NPM also restructures government organizations, dividing their sectors into smaller units and assigning responsibilities to those sectors.

In terms of Infrastructure Aspect, the gathered data resulted in a weighted mean of 2.31 indicating an Unsatisfactory rating. The respondents were satisfied with nine (9) out of 16 facilities present in the resettlement site including roads, streetlights, jeepneys, parking area, telephone lines, internet, basketball court, tricycle, and multipurpose hall. On the other hand, there were seven (7) out of 16 facilities that the respondents were dissatisfied with, specifically the evacuation center, the size of the unit, worn-out or broken fire hydrants, fire extinguishers, hoses within the building, inadequate lighting in the hallway, and the absence of the playground. According to Oplan LIKAS Operational Guidelines No. 1, Series of 2014, resettlement sites are required to include essential community facilities and social infrastructure. These include a church, playgrounds, a

multipurpose hall, adequate parking, access to the main road network, and an evacuation center.

The data indicated that on the day of the relocatees' transfer to the resettlement site, several essential facilities aimed at promoting the general welfare of the people were still lacking. All respondents reported the absence of the playground, and electricity in the covered court, chapel, and market at the site.

The primary aim of implementing the NPM is to secure better services for citizens. However, based on the results of the survey, several essential services and facilities were still missing when the affected families initially moved to the resettlement site. The relocatees felt that they were situated in a place far from their jobs, employment, and business, which brought additional burdens.

The relocatees' overall assessment of the services and facilities in CamRes1, covering socioeconomic, environmental, institutional, and infrastructure aspects, resulted in a weighted mean score of 2.46, or Unsatisfactory. According to the respondents, the displacement adversely affected their families and disrupted their previous way of life. To achieve sustainable development, it is crucial to ensure that people experience equitable and decent living conditions.

Based on the qualitative data collected from the FGD, the following analysis highlights the level of satisfaction of the respondents with the implementation of the ISF program:

Contentment. The key implementers emphasized that the families were uncontented with the government's ISF program. Mabilin (2014) stated that urban poor communities often resist relocation due to several factors, including limited employment opportunities, insufficient access to water and electricity, distance from educational institutions, and deficiencies in housing quality;

Frustrations. During the general assemblies held two (2) years before the actual relocation, the LGU and NHA provided information to the informal settlers and affected families regarding the monthly amortization and the available services and facilities, including water and electricity. However, according to the respondents, the facilities discussed during the general assembly, such as the market, were not present at the time of relocation;

Freedom of Choice. When asked to compare and given the opportunity to choose, the relocatees still preferred their previous dwellings despite their location in danger areas. Respondents indicated that life was more manageable there due to the availability of various livelihood opportunities and convenient access to essential services; and

Appreciation. Conversely, some respondents expressed gratitude for their relocation. They noted that the move was beneficial as they had previously experienced frequent flooding in their former residences. Additionally, others appreciated the

relocation because it provided them with housing when they previously did not own a home.

3. Areas of Concern that the Respondents Encountered in the Resettlement Site in terms of Socioeconomic, Environmental, Institutional, and Infrastructure Aspect

Based on the gathered data on the concerns of the relocatees at the new site, the LGU and NHA stated that the focus of the Oplan LIKAS is to relocate families immediately from the waterways and danger areas to ensure their safety during disasters and calamities. The implementers, using the allocated funds and budget from the 50B fund, made a concerted effort to comply with the guidelines' provisions, especially those related to the post-relocation programs. The program set specific goals for the LIAC, including government agencies, NGOs, and People's Organizations (POs), to transfer all the targeted families to the new site. The transfer of the relocatees pushed successfully achieving 100 percent of the scheduled ISFs being relocated. The immediate goal was the relocation itself, followed by subsequent site improvements. According to the New Public Management principles outlined by Osborne and Gaebler (1992), the government is required to ensure that citizens have access to essential services and support facilities, thereby enhancing overall service quality and effectiveness.

Based on the qualitative data gathered from the FGD with implementers and beneficiaries, the following analysis outlines the areas and concerns related to the implementation of the 1SF program:

Growing Population. The implementer stated that the transfer of families in the barangay resulted in a growing population which in turn increased the demand for services and facilities;

Unaffordability and incapacity to pay the amortization. The beneficiaries have expressed that the amortization rates for the housing units are unaffordable. According to all FGD respondents, poverty and unemployment significantly hinder most relocatees from meeting the amortization payments. The respondents recommended recalculating the overdue amounts and considering rubbing it back to zero, as many residents with arrears face the risk of having their units cancelled. As noted by Simbolon, Aulia, and Fachrudin (2021), subsidized housing should align with the targets and needs of low-income individuals.;

Community Support and Development. Based on the FGD with the implementer and the beneficiaries, there were several assistances provided to the relocatees in the form of financial and educational: scholarship and school supplies, manpower support, employment, livelihood, capital seeds, seminars, and skills training, processing of ISF documents, and the creation and organization of HOA; and

Unsustainability. When inquired about the status of livelihood assistance, all respondents stated that it is no longer available, and they did not pursue a business or

find employment aligned with the skills they had acquired from livelihood training sessions and seminars. The pandemic in 2019 depleted their financial and livelihood support from the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), and DILG, leaving them without the necessary budget to purchase essential ingredients or materials. Respondents expressed a desire for another opportunity to restart. This suggests that the families still lack empowerment. They have not developed a strong sense of ownership or self-reliance. Despite receiving start-up funds and skills training intended to facilitate income growth, they were unable to effectively manage and utilize these resources. According to Osborne and Gaebler (1992), New Public Management (NPM) seeks to empower citizens to become self-sufficient and improve their living conditions.

4. Recommendations of the Respondents to Address the Issues and Concerns they Encountered at the Resettlement Site

Based on the gathered data, the relocatees recommended the establishment of the following five (5) services and facilities at the CamRes1 resettlement site: 1) an individual water meter; 2) a lower amortization rate; 3) a safe sewerage treatment; 4) a market; and 5) functional CCTVs. These facilities received the most responses because relocatees consider it the most important to have or be improved at the resettlement site.

Osborne and Gaebler (1992) stated that in applying the NPM, the government shall adopt a private-sector style of management and forge partnerships with various stakeholders. This approach aims to facilitate the development and enhancement of resettlement sites, including the establishment of essential facilities.

Regarding livelihood and training programs recommended by the relocatees, the top preference is haircutting. This program is favored due to its minimal requirement for space and equipment; with basic tools such as scissors and a comb, relocatees can offer home services and earn a living. Massage or physical therapy ranks as the second-most popular livelihood program. Manicure/pedicure is the third-most recommended program, while soap-making and tailoring are fourth and fifth, respectively. Additionally, relocatees requested capital seed funding or initial support to start a business. They also requested an additional livelihood opportunity from the government.

Proposed Action Plan for the Enhanced Program on Relocation

Activities	Expected Output	Time frame	Target Participants	Resource	Sustainability Measures	Office Responsible
PRE-RELOCATION						
Workshop on the Formulation of Policy Guidelines on Relocation 1. Preparation of draft policy guidelines. 2. Identification of project goals and objectives through brainstorming and concept mapping	Policy Guidelines on Relocation	6 months	National Government Agencies (NGAs), Local Government Units (LGUs),	Logistics Manpower	Conduct quarterly meetings to monitor the status of the implementation of the program. Quarterly monitoring of the CSOs and	Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) Local Government Units (LGUs)

<p>3. Preparation of project outline from start to finish</p> <p>4. Presentation of the draft policy guidelines for comment and feedback from various stakeholders</p> <p>5. Finalization and approval of the policy guidelines</p> <p>6. Presentation of the final Policy Guidelines on Relocation</p>			<p>Civil Society Organizations (CSOs),</p> <p>Non-Government Organizations (NGOs),</p> <p>People's Organizations (PO),</p> <p>Informal Settler Families (ISFs)</p>		ISFs in the implementation of the program as planned	
<p>Creation of a Local Inter-Agency Committee (LIAC) composed of NGAs, LGUs, CSOs, NGOs, People's Organizations, and Informal Settler Families</p>	<p>Executive Order on the Creation of the LIAC</p>	<p>1 month</p>	<p>National Government Agencies (NGAs),</p> <p>Local Government Units (LGUs),</p> <p>Civil Society Organizations (CSOs),</p> <p>Informal Settler Families (ISFs)</p>	<p>Legislative Measure</p>	<p>Conduct of quarterly meeting</p> <p>Updating of the legal issuance, as necessary</p>	<p>Local Government Unit (LGU)</p>
<p>Identification of target and priority areas for relocation</p> <p>Tagging and Mapping of Structures</p>	<p>List of priority areas</p>	<p>3 months</p>	<p>National Government Agencies (NGAs),</p> <p>Local Government Units (LGUs)</p>	<p>Logistics Manpower</p>	<p>Regular updating of the list of priority areas</p> <p>Regular conduct of on-site inspection</p>	<p>Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR),</p> <p>Metro Manila Development Authority (MMDA)</p>
<p>Conduct of Situational Analysis</p>	<p>Situational Analysis Report</p>	<p>6 months</p>	<p>National Government Agencies,</p> <p>Local Government Units,</p> <p>Civil Society Organizations (CSOs),</p> <p>Non-Government Organizations (NGOs),</p> <p>People's Organizations (PO),</p>	<p>Logistics Manpower</p>	<p>Regular updating of the list of priority areas</p> <p>Regular conduct of on-site inspection</p> <p>Updating of LGU Data</p>	<p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO),</p> <p>City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO)</p>

			Informal Settler Families (ISFs)			
<p>Conduct of Census of ISFs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview with the ISFs (Household Heads) • Occupancy Verification • Pre-qualification of families • Master Listing of Households • Submission and completion of documents/requirements of the beneficiaries 	Master list of ISFs	6 months	Informal Settler Families (ISFs)	Logistics Manpower	<p>Regular conduct of on-site inspection</p> <p>Preparation of Quarterly Report on the Status of the ISFs</p> <p>Updating of LGU Data</p>	<p>National Housing Authority (NHA),</p> <p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)</p>
<p>Conduct of Consultation Dialogue with the affected ISFs for the identification of resettlement sites, housing options, financing scheme, and terms of payment</p>	List of Households	3 months	Informal Settler Families (ISFs)	Logistics Manpower	Regular conduct of consultation dialogue	<p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO),</p> <p>City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO)</p>
<p>Conduct of field trips to the resettlement site and Information drives</p>	<p>Field Trips Terminal Report</p> <p>IEC Materials</p>	3 months	Informal Settler Families (ISFs)	Logistics Manpower	Regular updating of available housing units	<p>National Housing Authority (NHA),</p> <p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)</p>
<p>Preparation of lists of available jobs and employment matched to the qualifications of the ISFs</p>	List of available jobs and employment	3 months	<p>City Social Welfare and Development Office,</p> <p>Public Employment and Services Office (PESO)</p>	Logistics Manpower	Regular Updating list of available jobs and employment	Public Employment and Services Office (PESO)
<p>Forging partnerships with nearby commercial and business establishments, government officers to endorse the list of possible job seekers</p>	Memorandum of Agreement	6 months	<p>National Government Agencies (NGAs),</p> <p>Local Government Units (LGUs)</p>	Logistics Manpower Legislation	Regular updating list of available jobs and employment	Public Employment and Services Office (PESO)
<p>Conduct of Social Preparation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • consultation dialogue with the affected ISFs • Interview per household <p>Psychosocial counseling per household</p>	Informed and empowered ISFs	6 months		Logistics Manpower	<p>Conduct House Visitation</p> <p>Conduct or progress monitoring and referral to other agencies if needed</p>	<p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO),</p> <p>City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO)</p>

<p>Conduct Self-Help Seminars and Training for the Affected Families</p> <p>I. Seminar on Values Formation II. Personal Development Course III. Self-Development Skills IV. Productivity V. Financial Literacy</p>	Empowered ISFs	6 months	Informal Settler Families	Logistics Manpower	<p>Regular conduct of dialogue with the ISFs</p> <p>Regular conduct of monitoring on the progress or improvement of the ISFs</p>	<p>City Social Welfare and Development Department (CSWDO),</p> <p>Public Employment and Services Office (PESO) of the LGU</p>
<p>Identification of available housing units with complete social services and facilities, or</p>	Housing units with complete facilities	6 months	<p>National Government Agencies (NGAs),</p> <p>Local Government Units (LGUs)</p>	Logistics Manpower	Regular site inspection	<p>National Housing Authority (NHA),</p> <p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO),</p> <p>City Engineering</p>
<p>Construction of new buildings/houses with complete social services and facilities</p>	Housing units with complete facilities	3 years		Logistics Manpower	Regular conduct of progress monitoring	<p>National Housing Authority (NHA),</p> <p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO),</p> <p>City Engineering</p>
<p>Workshop on the Formulation of the People's Plan</p>	People's Plan	2 months	<p>Civil Society Organizations (CSOs),</p> <p>Non-Government Organizations (NGOs),</p> <p>Informal Settler Families (ISFs)</p>	Logistics Manpower	<p>Regular conduct of progress monitoring</p> <p>Updating if necessary</p>	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)
<p>Workshop on the Formulation of the Resettlement and Relocation Action Plan (RRAP)</p> <p>1. Preparation of draft RRAP 2. Presentation of the draft RRAP for comments and feedback from various stakeholders 3. Mainstreaming or integration of People's Plan in the RRAP 4. Finalization of the RRAP 5. Presentation of the final RRAP</p>	Resettlement and Relocation Action Plan	2 months	<p>National Government Agencies,</p> <p>Local Government Units,</p> <p>Civil Society Organizations (CSOs),</p> <p>Non-Government Organizations (NGOs),</p>	Logistics Manpower Legislation	<p>Regular conduct of progress monitoring</p> <p>Updating if necessary</p>	<p>National Housing Authority (NHA),</p> <p>Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)</p> <p>City Planning and Development Department (CPDD)</p>

			People's Organizations (PO), Informal Settler Families (ISFs)			
Conduct of Pre-demolition Conference	PDC Report	1 month	National Government Agencies (NGAs), Local Government Units (LGUs)	Logistics Manpower Legislation	Regular conduct of on-site inspection Conduct of patrol in the cleared areas Turn-over to the barangay	National Housing Authority (NHA), Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO), Barangay
II. ACTUAL RELOCATION						
Setting up of Relocation Action Center (RAC)	Established RAC	2 weeks	National Government Agencies (NGAs), Local Government Units (LGUs (City and Barangay)	Logistics Manpower	Provision of logistics to the RAC	National Housing Authority (NHA), Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)
Transfer of relocatees to the relocation sites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provision of assistance of the community leaders during the transfer; ▪ Distribution of food assistance ▪ Securing the belongings of the relocatees; ▪ Monitoring of transferred families (count, survey of immediate assistance) 	100% transferred ISFs	3 months	National Government Agencies (NGAs), Local Government Units (City Barangay)	Logistics Manpower	Close monitoring of the status of the transfer Collaboration of various agencies in transit to the resettlement site	National Housing Authority (NHA), Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO), Barangay, Community Leaders, Volunteer, ISFs
Turn-over of the housing units to the relocatees	Relocatees provided with housing units List of relocatees with Housing Units	3 months	Relocatees	Manpower Legislative Measure	Regular monitoring of the relocatees Regular updating of the list of relocated families	National Housing Authority (NHA), Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)
Documentation of the actual relocation	Report on Relocation	2 weeks	National Government Agencies (NGAs), Local Government Units	Manpower	Preparation of report immediately after the conclusion of the activity Report to the Local Chief Executive	Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)

			Informal Settler Families (ISFs)			
III. POST RELOCATION PHASE						
Creation of Home Owners Association <ul style="list-style-type: none"> General HOA HOA per building/ Area 	Organized HOA	1 month	Relocatees	Logistics Manpower	Accreditation to the LGU	National Housing Authority (NHA), Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)
Conduct dialogue with the relocatees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One week after the relocation Quarterly in the first year; Annual general assembly for three years 	1. Post Activity Report 2. Situational Analysis 3. Comparative Analysis of the Living condition of the Households 4. List of households still living on the site	1 month	Relocatees	Logistics Manpower	LGU (HARO) and HOA	Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)
Provision of livelihood to the relocatees unique to each household	Financially stable relocatees	6 months	Relocatees	Logistics Manpower		Public Employment Service Office (PESO), City Social Welfare and Development Department (CSWDO)
Conduct of capacity building for the relocatees: 1. Skills training 2. Livelihood seminars/ training 3. Microenterprise 4. Entrepreneurship	Skilled and trained relocatees	2 months	National Government Agencies (NGAs), Local Government Units Informal Settler Families (ISFs)	Logistics Manpower Legislation		Public Employment Service Office (PESO), Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) Technical Education and Skills Development Agency (TESDA)
Conduct of annual job fair	List of hired relocatees	1 month	Relocatees, Private Companies	LGU in partnership with DOLE, TESDA and	Regular updating of the list of relocatees	Public Employment Service Office (PESO) Department of Labor and

						Employment (DOLE) Technical Education and Skills Development Agency (TESDA)
Conduct Results-based Monitoring and Evaluation (RBME) on the Status of the Relocatees, services, facilities, and livelihood in the resettlement site 5. Quarterly in the first year 6. Annual for three years	RBME Report	3 months	Relocatees	Logistics Manpower Legislation	Regular updating of the system Installation of a firewall to protect the system	Housing and Resettlement Office (HARO)
Development of a database containing the following information: I. Households II. Services and facilities III. Livelihood IV. Microenterprise/businesses	Database	6 months	System Developer	Logistics Manpower Legislation	Regular updating of the system Installation of a firewall to protect the system	Information and Technology Office (ITO)
Development of a website for the issues and concerns of the relocatees to be managed by the LGU and accessible by the NGAs	Website	6 months	System Developer	Logistics Manpower Legislation	Regular updating of the system Installation of a firewall to protect the system	Information and Technology Office (ITO)

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Citizen participation, or citizen control, refers to the maximum feasible involvement of the citizens in a program and is the categorical term of citizen power. This study evaluated the extent of the affected families' participation in the three stages of relocation under the 1SF Program, or Oplan LIKAS. According to Sherry R. Arnstein's typology from "A Ladder of Citizen Participation" (1969), which outlines eight levels of participation, the affected families' involvement in implementing Oplan LIKAS can be categorized at the fourth level: Consultation. This level signifies a degree of tokenism, where powerholders allow the underprivileged to voice their opinions but retain the ultimate decision-making authority, as described by Arnstein (1969).

Tokenism is a "participatory" strategy that is best described as a token gesture or a meaningless attempt at involving citizens. According to Arnstein (1969), tokenism can take the form of information-only procedures or consultation processes that have minimal or no impact on changing the status quo. In Arnstein's typology of the Eight Ladders of Citizen

Participation, consultation is identified as the fourth level. The study indicates that consultation alone does not ensure that citizen concerns and ideas are genuinely considered. When powerholders restrict participation to this level, it can become a mere ceremonial act with little real influence.

The RRAP formulation invited the CSOs to participate in the potential mainstreaming of the People's Plan, involving a select group of individuals or LIAC members. Although the people were involved in the program's implementation, they lacked the authority to ensure that the LGU would consider their opinions, as the ultimate decision-making authority remained with the powerholders. According to Arnstein (1969), this level of participation does not guarantee that the power holders will take into account the citizens' concerns.

The methods employed by the government, such as information dissemination through news media, flyers, pamphlets, posters, consultation meetings, general assemblies, and Kumustahan dialogues, were just one-way communication or vehicles from the officials to the citizens. According to Arnstein (1969), restricting participation to this level results in no follow-through, which in turn prevents any change in the status quo. Consequently, the plan remains merely a blueprint, and its implementation may or may not occur. People held the belief that they had already gained power and were actively involved, yet those who perceived themselves as part of the process merely engaged in participation, serving as the program's driving force.

Arnstein (1969) noted that informing citizens about their rights, responsibilities, and options is a crucial step toward genuine citizen participation. The government provided information at the late stage of planning when it had already determined and laid down all the steps and procedures to undertake, leaving little room for negotiation. Implementing planning instruments is crucial for efficient resource allocation and maintaining environmental balance for sustainable urban development. (Nisa, Umilia, Rahmawati, and Samsura, 2023)

Upon measuring the level of satisfaction with the implementation of the 1SF Program since the relocation of the families to CamRes1 in 2015, the researcher found that while some of the plans and programs outlined in Operational Guidelines No. 01 S. 2014, also known as Guidelines in the Transfer of ISF from Danger Areas in the NCR, were successfully implemented, the majority were not.

However, despite the passage of almost a decade, the government still needed to establish other essential basic services and facilities. The findings indicate that the relocatees expressed dissatisfaction with their relocation site, citing various issues and concerns that the government needs to tackle.

The objective of the 1SF Program is to achieve inclusive growth, improved human development, and total community development; however, based on the results and findings of the research, it may be concluded that these aspects were not met. Generally, the families in CamRes1 continue to live below the poverty line, eagerly awaiting

government assistance. Still, the families are requesting assistance to meet their basic needs. According to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, if the basic needs remain unmet, we cannot meet the next hierarchy of needs.

Moreover, although for others, the housing units were affordable, some scholars relate affordability to income, where affordability is the relationship between relative price and income. These scholars include Stone (1994), Robinson, Scobie, and Hallinan (2006), and Ndubueze, Gan, and Hill (2009). In general, due to the loss of jobs, income, and inadequate jobs near the site, the majority of the family members were either jobless or unemployed. Consequently, they were unable to pay the amortization, as they had already budgeted their money for their subsistence.

This is one of the reasons why others leased or sold their units and went to Metro Manila with business centers, where they had a chance of finding jobs. According to Cadavid (2010), poverty recycling occurs when impoverished slum dwellers are unable to maintain their new living conditions, leading them to sell or rent their dwellings and return to the slums.

The results showed that although the relocatees are now living in a safer place than their previous dwellings in waterways and dangerous areas, the relocation had negative effects on the people's lives, including loss of income, displacement, changing schools, changing places of work, and alienation. The study concludes that the government should ensure the availability and completeness of all basic services and facilities at the resettlement site before relocating the ISF. This action will guarantee the fulfillment of the families' needs.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the conducted survey and focus group discussions with key implementers and beneficiaries, here are the recommendations.

The government is constantly advocating and promoting participatory governance, citizen engagement, and the whole-of-nation approach in all programs, projects, and activities, affirming that the citizens will be involved in the process, particularly the target beneficiaries or affected populace. However, the government missed the mark by not realizing the real definition and essence of participatory governance through other lenses.

Activities such as information dissemination campaigns, consultation dialogues, and meetings only provide a general understanding of the program's concept and façade, often using technical jargon that is difficult for ordinary people to comprehend. This is also a contributing factor to the government's inability to meet the objectives and expected output of certain programs, which often end in failure and ultimately result in a waste of government resources.

Multi-stakeholders, primarily the beneficiaries and affected populace, should participate in all stages of the development process, including planning, implementation,

monitoring, and evaluation. Participants should actively participate in the process, not just show up. The participants must produce a valuable output to integrate into the government's plan.

In the project development, it is recommended that the government engage the stakeholders, particularly the target beneficiaries and affected families, in identifying the goals and objectives, the expected outcome of the program, and the likelihood that it will be successful.

Most importantly, stakeholders will be involved in planning or preparing the project's outline from start to finish, concept mapping, brainstorming, and drawing the bigger picture of the project.

In the LGUs, accredited CSOs are operating in the locality, which could help in providing ideas, concepts, and designs. These groups could lay the groundwork for developing a more appropriate intervention that directly addresses the issues, concerns, and needs of the community.

The decision-makers should also base the policy guidelines and development plan on the situation reports and the evidence gathered during the situation analysis and evaluation process. The decision-makers could use it as a first tool for formulating policies and plans, methods and approaches, allocating resources, and drafting legislation.

The study highlights the need to formulate a resettlement program through in-depth research, strategic planning, institutional building, active participation from both sending and receiving communities, detailed preparation, execution in accordance with established policies and guidelines, and monitoring and evaluation of the program's output and impact.

The key players could use expectation mapping to determine the people's and government's perspectives on the project and the expected result. When thoughts and ideas align, they can see a unified big picture.

Subsequently, the group may also map the concerns to understand the risks that might arise during the program. This will ensure the fulfillment of the people's needs and desires. Resettlement planning should be comprehensive to achieve the goals and objectives. It is recommended to include both sending and receiving LGUs in the planning workshop to balance both parties' expectations. This approach ensures that the formulated plan benefits both groups, preventing discrimination and resource competition.

The data recommends using a grassroots, bottom-up approach to actively engage the target beneficiaries in all phases of project development. The 1SF, or Oplan LIKAS Program, utilized a top-down approach, involving community participation solely at the informing stage, as per Arnstein's (1969) ladder of citizen participation. The policy

guidelines, which form the foundation of every program, did not incorporate community participation.

In the implementation of the ISF Program, the main consideration is the prompt completion of the relocation based on the regulations and set standards. The number of relocated ISFs and the number of units provided became the measure of the program's success, rather than the fulfillment of the people's needs and their participation in the undertaking. In the execution of the plan, the stakeholders should play a vital role, not just as mere observers but as active partners. During the actual relocation process, community leaders may volunteer to assist their fellow relocatees.

To determine the program's impact, the government should continue to monitor and evaluate the relocatees situation. The government can utilize this information to establish a comparison between the living conditions of the relocated individuals before and after the move. This will help the decision-makers and powerholders take the necessary legislative actions and provide immediate interventions to address the issues and concerns of the people.

They can use results-based monitoring and evaluation (RBME) to analyze and evaluate the PPAs' outputs, outcomes, and impact. Apply this at all program stages to track performance and assess the project's long-term outcomes, not just its short-term ones. The result will serve as the basis for identifying areas for improvement to further enhance the government's future developmental projects, taking into account all sectoral aspects and stakeholders.

Additionally, the people will engage in monitoring the project and evaluate the integration of the agreements made during the initiation and planning phases. The CSOs, NGOs, POs, and beneficiaries shall keep track of whether the government's projects achieve the intended purpose.

Further, to achieve inclusive growth, the beneficiaries shall be considered active partners in the development process. They should not be considered an audience where their signatures on the attendance sheets measure the success of the programs in attaining their purpose and objectives.

In general, before the national or local government proceeds with the relocation, they have to ensure that the basic services and facilities necessary for the promotion of the general welfare of the people are present, complete, and functional, and they shall continuously expand and modernize the facilities in the resettlement sites.

The government shall continuously expand and modernize the resettlement sites through e-governance by using information and communications technology in the resettlement programs. It will promote transparency, accountability, efficiency, and effectiveness in service delivery. The government should create a database to monitor and evaluate the condition of relocated families. The database could include information on the site's infrastructure, including its functional status, the number and demographics

of the relocated families, the availability of basic services and facilities in the community, the livelihoods of the people, and the provision of capacity-building programs. The NGA and the concerned LGU will be responsible for its management. Other stakeholders, such as NGOs, CSOs, and POs, may view the system to identify their entry points where they could help the government and the people. This would allow the government to prepare a comparative analysis of the panel of data to assess the people's living conditions.

The government may also develop a website as a platform for people to voice their concerns about the resettlement site, their conditions, and the necessary interventions to address these concerns. The government may use it to continuously track and monitor the status of the relocatees.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For ethical considerations, the researchers obtained the informed consent of the respondents of the study, assured the strict confidentiality of the information, and that the identity would be protected. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and the results were used purely for research.

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